

THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Nurullayeva Farida Sherali qizi

Student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

raxmatilloquldoshev@gmail.com

Muradullayeva Malika Zayniddinovna

Student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

murodullayevamalika9006@gmail.com

***Abstract:** Language is a social phenomenon, the most important means of communication between people and communities. Today, the demand for learning foreign languages is increasing. The President is creating many conditions for learning foreign languages. Nowadays, English is widely taught in almost all educational institutions. The use of technologies in the process of learning these foreign languages gives effective results.*

***Keywords:** foreign language, modern approach, multimedia, pedagogical technology, methodology.*

With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the unique features of our time, special attention is being paid to using its possibilities, to fully approach the educational process and to organize it. The 21st century is the age of high technologies, and our modern youth are taking steps not only in accordance with the spirit of the times, but also in accordance with the progress in the electronic world. For this reason, a different approach to the process of teaching the young generation is required. The role of the teacher in the lessons is also changing. The teacher now acts mainly as a guide. It is time for

teachers who aim to keep pace with the times to be ready to enliven any part of the lesson through ICT. In the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" "Introduction of advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies" by way of teaching the growing young generation to foreign languages, fundamentally improving the system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently, and on the basis of this, their achievements in world development and wide use of world information resources, international cooperation and communication "creating conditions and opportunities for their development" and the need to implement a number of important tasks for this.

In this document, starting from the 2013-2014 academic year, foreign languages will be taught in the first grades of general secondary schools in the form of games, and then as the main subject of education using ICT tools. In accordance with this important decision, today, in particular, foreign language lessons were looked at more deeply. In order to protect the country's honor on the world stage, our youth must first be able to compete with their foreign peers. conducted in English, the international business language. In fact, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, in the purposeful organization of game-based lessons that are interesting to students, is very large. is becoming an integral part of the educational process. In order to teach young people English through a computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. it also includes the ability to organize new educational programs based on it. In order to become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-based English language teaching has several advantages compared to traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English language learner has four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will be able to test their skills. Currently,

this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education. In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every concept unit taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of a computer is better stored in the student's memory. The fact that it can be delivered in the form of video makes teaching foreign languages through the computer one of the most effective methods. That is why I want to use the rich possibilities of the computer to teach the English language to 5th graders through the computer. Basically, it is appropriate to use Word and Power Point programs to explain current topics. Because I think that students will understand much easier if the topic is explained using table views through the Word program. In Power Point, students can be more attracted to the topic by showing these topics in audio, picture and video formats. As stated by our President I. Karimov in his works entitled "High Spirituality-Yengilmaskuch": "If you want to glorify our Uzbekistan to the world, glorify its ancient history and bright future, if you want to keep it forever in the memory of generations, first of all We need to educate young great writers, great poets, and great artists." Therefore, learning a foreign language is a requirement of the current era, and developing new methods of language learning for the young generation based on the "National Personnel Training Program" , recommendation for the study process is one of the urgent issues facing scientists and specialists. In order for our talented young people to become mature specialists in their fields of interest, first of all, they need to have a perfect knowledge of any foreign language, including English. Therefore, introducing technologies and ensuring that teaching methods meet the requirements of the time are the main tasks of pedagogues-scientists that cannot be delayed. While the economic, political, cultural and educational relations of our country with the countries of the world are growing, the interest of our youth in the life, culture, customs, and language of foreign countries is increasing. In the development of these relations, the role of foreign languages, especially English, is incomparable.

Today, learning foreign languages has become a necessity. After the independence of our country, the demand for learning foreign languages is increasing and not decreasing. In Uzbekistan, the Internet is highly developed, so that a language learner can use all the facilities necessary for him. Currently, all schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher education institutions have modern computers through which any user can access the Internet. The main goal of using modern technologies in learning foreign languages is to facilitate language learning without difficulty. The most common method of modern approaches is mainly the use of multimedia in the lesson. The useful side of multimedia tools in learning a foreign language is a live game, you can learn by looking at pictures, listening to sounds, and watching the activity of live games. One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech." By teaching the real language, the Internet helps to build speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language. Nowadays, many conditions have been created for learning foreign languages. You can learn in different ways, especially through the Internet. Various sites on the Internet will help you learn these foreign languages. For example, sites useful for learning English: List-english.ru - various materials for learning English: online dictionaries, schools, forums, translators, tutors, tests, school textbooks, video courses, games, Android apps, iPhone, YouTube channels, podcasts and more. Everything is free. Englishtips.org — Downloadable textbooks and books. The search engine works well. You can find many things related to language learning. Britishcouncil.org is the website of the British Council. Quizzes, grammar, games and more. Everything is in English, so for those new to the language, it can be a little difficult to navigate, but it will strengthen the knowledge. Real-english.com is a site full of lessons, articles and

videos. Eslpod.com - its main mission is to teach English as a second language. 19 Ello.org is the bomb for middle school teachers and students. It will be possible to achieve development and progress only when new ideas and technologies are used in teaching English. There is no doubt that if they are followed during training, it will have a good effect. The purpose of using additional text teaching technology is to familiarize students with the most general ideas in education. This technology reflects a person-oriented approach, it is possible to achieve productive, positive results only if each student acquires knowledge, skills and abilities, but also takes into account the individual characteristics of his development. Children like to watch cartoons on TV. If we take advantage of this and take a cartoon that they often watch, translate it into another foreign language, for example, English, and give it to them, it would be easier for children to memorize and remember words. At first they would talk about themselves, then about others and about various events in their lives. In addition, it is possible to teach children a foreign language by posting various cartoons and short films through YouTube. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects, i.e. reading, writing, listening and speaking, and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language, reading, writing, listening and speaking. For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation,

adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. School, listey and college foreign language courses are fundamentally different from other subjects taught in them. The concept of "foreign language" can be interpreted as follows: the methodological term "learning a foreign language" means acquiring the skills and abilities of speaking, listening, reading and writing in this language. In recent years, it has been observed that people's personal and professional communication is becoming more active with the help of information communication technologies. For a long time, writing was important only as a means of teaching a foreign language. However, the need to effectively use various forms of official and personal correspondence is clearly visible in the current era. Therefore, the formation of the written speech of students studying the Turkish language is also important. Pedagogical technology is a method of systematic creation, application of the FLT process and mutual cooperation for the purposes of identifying and obtaining knowledge and optimizing their educational forms with the help of technical and human resources. Technology can also be manifested at the level of operations, education and actions in the educational process. Conclusion: In conclusion, language is the wealth of society, it implements the interaction of society members, it gathers knowledge about all events in existence. As a result of the use of innovative technologies during the study of foreign languages, students' interest in the lesson increases and it becomes easier to master the lessons. In the era of advanced technology, it is necessary to perfectly learn and teach foreign languages in a way that is understandable to everyone, using these facilities.

Newspapers. Newspapers can be brought easily to the class in various subjects and courses, especially in literature, language classes, history, geography etc. Some of them possess precious information for these subjects, but we should know how to separate this information. Teachers and students use newspapers according to their

purposes in different ways. Newspapers can be used for the culture they carry. The more widely learners read, the greater they understand this culture and its meaning. Newspapers can be also used for depicting changes in the language as and helping students and teachers to keep up pace with these changes. Many newspapers are linguistically new and provide valuable linguistic information. They can be used for the broad variety of text sorts and language styles, rarely found in books. Newspapers are very good source for ESP teachers. They can be used as teaching materials to improve students' language skills. Some newspapers are easily read and easily used. Teachers can design exercises to increase reading comprehension, critical thinking skills, writing skills, grammar skills, vocabulary. The teachers should pay attention to the way how to organize a clear activity using them when they have a lot of newspapers and information [3, 157]. Newspapers are mostly suitable for mixedability classes, depending on the activity, questions. While planning a lesson using a newspaper, the teacher should take into account the paragraph, the density of information, the length of the article, the complexity of the language, the content, the time available and the level of the students' knowledge.

Radio. Radio has an important share in creating pictures in the mind through the power of words, in developing people's imagination, it encourages the imagination to fill in the visuals. The listeners can see the drama in their minds. Thus, when radio is used in the classroom it aids students to voice their creativity, to develop their imagination. Radio programs help to learn a language. Radio not only gives new information and entertainment, in language classes it helps the pronunciation, the intonation, the pitch of voice. Students gain a feeling of satisfaction from having understood something of a real podcast and we can see the joy in their faces. They can develop great confidence in their ability to cope with English as it's spoken out of the classroom. Students can use BBC World Service news bulletin, Voice of America and other foreign radio stations. In such cases students have no possibilities, the teacher can record the news bulletin, transcribe it and prepare to explain any difficult vocabulary that may come out. Television. Television programs can be used as

warming-up activities, pre-activities for the issue, as a supplementary material for a certain topic, for up-to-date information, to update the information in the textbooks. Documentaries on Civil War, on Wildlife, on Discovery Channel, and others, have opened valuable windows for the students. Through these documentaries students learn about cultures, languages, science and others. Some of these documentaries, if carefully selected can be used efficiently in the classrooms and be a part of the curriculum. They help students for better understanding of the subject. As we cannot use TV information when it is given, we can bring this information into the classroom by videotaping different TV programs for later use.

CONCLUSION

Mass Media helps teachers make teaching and learning visual. A picture tells a thousand words and it helps students develop their thinking and observation skills, it promotes imagination. Media helps with several issues such as: motivation, editing, recycling, drafting, clarity, revising, mixed-ability classes, variety, updating information in the book, giving life and color to lesson procedures and methods, thus at the same time helping the students improve fluency and accuracy.

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